

Supplementary Material

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Figure S1: Direct Olsen cycle implemented on one BST MLC under 700 V (195 kV cm^{-1}) from $-70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The harvested energy is 45.2 mJ, corresponding to 2.9 J cm^{-3} .

Figure S2: Direct Olsen cycle implemented on one BST MLC under 1100 V (306 kV cm^{-1}) from $-60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The harvested energy is 56.6 mJ, corresponding to 3.6 J cm^{-3} .